

THEORETICAL STUDY OF THE PROCESS OF FEEDING CLOVER HEAP TO THE
CONVEYOR OF A DRYING PLANT

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Abstract. The article presents the results of canonical transformations of a mathematical model when studying the process of leveling a heap of forage crops onto a drying conveyor. During the canonical transformation of an equation, the origin of coordinates is transferred to a new point and the old axes are rotated by a certain angle in the factor space, as a result of which the linear terms disappear and the value of the free term changes. Based on the found coefficients, a second-order regression equation was compiled. The coordinates of the new center were found by solving a system of differential equations. To determine the regression coefficients in canonical form, the characteristic equation was solved. As a result of the calculations, the values of the regression coefficients were obtained.

Key words: optimum, search, definition, indicator, unevenness, leveling, heap of forage crops, material feed rates, conveyor, dryer, experiment, factor, planning matrix, criterion, regression coefficient, optimization parameter, hypothesis, adequacy, experimental errors, dispersion, statistical evaluation

Introduction. When studying complex processes in which several factors participate and interact, the task of their optimization is multifactorial, and its solution can be significantly accelerated by using special methods of experimental planning and obtaining a mathematical model of the object of study. To describe the optimum region under conditions of heterogeneity, Box and Benkin developed rotatable three-level plans using the second-order regression equation. The center of the experiment was chosen taking into account the data from the implementation of the steep ascent program at a new point, which is located closer to the optimal response value [1,5].

Materials and results. After describing the optimum region and obtaining an adequate mathematical model of the second order, it is necessary to determine the coordinates of the point corresponding to the optimal value of the optimization parameter and study the properties of the response surface in its vicinity [1,2,3].

A second-order regression equation was composed based on the coefficients found

$$Y = 10,833 - 2,3625 X_4 + 3,175 X_5 + 3,2375 X_8 + 0,075 X_4 X_5 + 0,05 X_4 X_8 - 0,825 X_5 X_6 + 0,4085 2 X_4 + 1,7835 2 X_5 + 1,8585 \quad (1)$$

After describing the optimum region and obtaining an adequate mathematical model of the second order, it is necessary to determine the coordinates of the point corresponding to the optimal value of the optimization parameter and study the properties of the response surface in its vicinity. To study the nature of the response surface in the stationary region, we carry out the regression equation (1) to a canonical form of the form

$$Y = Y_s B_{11} X_1^2 + B_{22} X_2^2 + B_{33} X_3^2 \quad (2)$$

where Y – the value of the optimization criterion;

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Y_S – the value of the optimization criterion at the optimal point;

x_i – new coordinate axes;

B_{ii} – regression coefficients in canonical form.

In the canonical transformation of the equation, the origin of coordinates is transferred to a new point S and the old axes are rotated by a certain angle in the factor space, as a result of which the linear terms disappear and the value of the free term changes [4,6]. The coordinates of the new center were found by solving the system of differential equations.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dY}{dX_4} = -2,3625 + 0,075X_5 + 0,05X_8 + 0,817X_4 = 0 \\ \frac{dY}{dX_5} = 3,175 + 0,075X_4 - 0,825X_8 + 3,567X_5 = 0 \\ \frac{dY}{dX_8} = 3,2375 + 0,05X_4 - 0,825X_5 + 3,717X_8 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

and by solving equation (1) and substituting the obtained values of the factors into it, we determined the value of the optimization parameter at the point

$$S(Y_S)$$

To determine the regression coefficients in canonical form, the characteristic equation was solved

$$f_{(B)} = \begin{vmatrix} 0,4085 - B & 0,0375 & 0,025 \\ 0,0375 & 1,7835 - B & -0,4125 \\ 0,025 & -0,4125 & 1,8585 - B \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The solution of equations (4) was performed on a computer. As a result of calculations, the following values of the coefficients were obtained: $B_{44} = 0,40428$; $B_{55} = 1,42699$; $B_{88} = 2,21873$. The regression equation (1) presented in canonical form has the form

$$Y - 3,329 = 0,40428 X_4^2 + 1,42699 X_5^2 + 2,21873 X_8^2 \quad (5)$$

Выводы. Thus, it is established that the center of the figure is located near the experimental region and the a priori chosen center of the experiment. Since all coefficients at quadratic terms have positive signs, the response surface described by equation (1) is a three-dimensional paraboloid with coordinates of the center of the surface: $X_{4S} = 3,0770$; $X_{5S} = 1,2289$; $X_{8S} = 1,1852$ (the factors have the following values: drum rotation frequency – 45.4 rad/s, material feed speed – 7.4 10⁻³ m/s, pile layer height – 0.78 m).

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